

Ruthenium(III) catalysed polymerization of acrylonitrile with aminoalcohols in presence of CCl_4

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The kinetics of ruthenium(III) catalysed polymerization of acrylonitrile (AN) with aminoalcohols (AA) viz. ethanolamine, diethanolamine and triethanolamine in presence of CCl_4 and in dimethylsulfoxide medium have been studied. When $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] \leq 1$, the initiation process appears to involve AA, Ru^{3+} and CCl_4 and rate of polymerization (R_p) has a first order dependence on AN and a half order dependence in each of CCl_4 , Ru^{3+} and AA. However, when $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] > 1$, the initiation appears to involve AA, Ru^{3+} and AN and rate of polymerization had a 1.4 order dependence on AN and a half order dependence on each of Ru^{3+} and AA. The suitable mechanisms consistent with kinetic data have been proposed.

The kinetics of polymerization of vinyl monomers initiated by charge-transfer mechanism in presence of CCl_4 have been studied by many investigators¹. Recently Pd^{II} and Ru^{III} catalysed polymerization of methylmethacrylate by amines and aminoalcohols in presence of CCl_4 ² indicated the participation of charge-transfer complex between catalyst-amine adduct and CCl_4 or monomer during the polymerization. In order to throw more light on the nature of these catalysts, we have studied the Ru^{III} catalysed polymerization of acrylonitrile (AN) by amino-alcohols (AA) viz. ethanolamine (EA), diethanolamine (DEA) and triethanolamine (TEA) in presence of CCl_4 in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) medium and the results are reported in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The polymerization of AN was carried out in the absence of either AA or CCl_4 at 50–65°C and no polymer was formed which clearly indicates that the polymerization definitely requires the presence of both AA and CCl_4 . Fig. 1 represents the typical plots between percent conversion and time for the polymerization of AN in the presence of EA, DEA and TEA at 60°C. It is apparent from Fig. 1 that the percent conversion increases linearly with time and was found to increase when EA was replaced by DEA and TEA.

The effect of $[\text{AN}]$ on rate of polymerization (R_p) was studied at 60°C under the experimental conditions, $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] \leq 1$ and $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] > 1$. An increase in $[\text{AN}]$ increases R_p under both the experimental conditions at constant $[\text{RuCl}_3]$, the catalyst. The monomer exponent values under

Fig. 1. Relationship between % conversion and time at 60°C for polymerization of AN, $[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{EA}] = 1.57 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DEA}] = 0.98 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{TEA}] = 0.71 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

both the conditions have been evaluated from the plots of $\log(R_p)$ versus $\log[\text{AN}]$ (Figs. 2a and b). The monomer exponent values were found to be 1.0 ± 0.05 and 1.35 ± 0.05 under the conditions, $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] \leq 1$ and $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] > 1$, respectively. The varying monomer exponent values indicate the different types of mechanisms under the two different $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}]$ ratios.

Fig. 2. Relationship between $\log(R_p)$ and $\log[AN]$ at 60°C in DMSO medium. (a) $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] \leq 1$: $[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{EA}] = 1.57 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DEA}] = 0.98 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{TEA}] = 0.71 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (b) $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] > 1$: $[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{EA}] = 0.35 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DEA}] = 0.49 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{TEA}] = 0.88 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Table 1 shows the effect of $[\text{CCl}_4]$ on R_p at 60°C . It was observed that R_p was proportional to $[\text{CCl}_4]^{1/2}$ when $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] \leq 1$. However, the R_p was found to be independent of $[\text{CCl}_4]$, when $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] > 1$, which substantiates the operation of the different mechanisms. The plots of $\log(R_p)$ versus $\log[AA]$ (Fig. 3) were linear with slopes of about 0.5 under both the conditions showing that R_p is proportional to $[\text{AA}]^{0.5}$.

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log(R_p)$ versus $\log[AA]$ at 60°C in DMSO medium, $[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The results of the study of the effect of $[\text{RuCl}_3]$ on R_p (Fig. 4) were in agreement with equation,

$$R_p = a + b [\text{RuCl}_3]^{0.5}$$

where a is the rate of uncatalysed polymerization.

An increase in the concentration of hydroquinone, a well known retarder, decreased R_p in presence of EA, DEA and TEA providing evidence for the free radical polymerization (Table 2). The values of energy of activation (E_{act}) and enthalpy change (ΔH^\ddagger) were in order EA > DEA > TEA (Table 3).

Table 1. Effect of $[\text{CCl}_4]$ on the R_p at 60°C

$[\text{CCl}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$R_p, 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] \leq 1^a$			$[\text{CCl}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$R_p, 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ $[\text{CCl}_4]/[\text{AA}] > 1^b$		
	EA	DEA	TEA		EA	DEA	TEA
0.19	0.35	0.60	0.85	0.79	3.62	4.10	5.05
0.38	0.55	0.80	1.15	0.97	3.80	4.35	5.25
0.60	0.75	1.05	1.45	1.17	3.85	4.30	5.40
0.79	0.85	1.20	1.65	1.95	3.80	4.33	5.45
0.97	0.90	1.30	1.80	-	-	-	-

$[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

^a $[\text{EA}]$, $[\text{DEA}]$ and $[\text{TEA}] = 1.57, 0.98$ and 0.95 mol dm^{-3} , respectively. ^b $[\text{EA}]$, $[\text{DEA}]$ and $[\text{TEA}] = 0.78, 0.49$ and 0.35 mol dm^{-3} , respectively.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\log(R_p)$ versus $[\text{RuCl}_3]^{0.5}$ at 60°C in DMSO medium, $[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{EA}] = 1.57 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DEA}] = 0.98 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{TEA}] = 0.71 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Table 2. Effect of [hydroquinone] on the R_p of AN at 60°C

[Hydroquinone] mol dm^{-3}	$R_p, 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$		
	EA	DEA	TEA
0	2.30	2.80	3.49
0.114	1.50	2.10	3.02
0.227	0.70	1.40	2.10

$[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. $[\text{EA}]$, $[\text{DEA}]$ and $[\text{TEA}] = 1.57, 0.98$ and 0.71 mol dm^{-3} , respectively.

Intrinsic viscosity ($[\eta]_{\text{int}}$), degree of polymerization (\bar{P}_n) and average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) for the polymers prepared are given in Table 4. \bar{P}_n is seen to increase almost linearly with increase in $[\text{AN}]$ in presence of each aminoalcohol.

Mechanism of polymerization :

There are reports³ that the polymerization of vinyl monomers by amine and CCl_4 is vastly accelerated by transition metal-ions like Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ru^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , etc. In some cases,

Table 4. $[\eta]_{\text{int}}$, \bar{M}_v and \bar{P}_n for the polymerization of AN of 60°C

Aminoalcohol	$[\text{AN}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\eta]_{\text{int}}$	\bar{P}_n	\bar{M}_v
Ethanolamine	0.85	0.44	508	26982
	1.43	0.55	684	36331
	2.14	0.78	1091	57889
	2.86	1.10	1725	91550
	3.57	1.45	2500	132650
Diethanolamine	4.29	1.79	3311	172718
	0.85	0.47	555	29462
	1.43	0.60	768	40801
	2.14	0.82	1162	61880
	2.86	1.02	1560	82782
Triethanolamine	3.57	1.17	1868	99138
	4.29	1.38	2325	123395
	0.85	0.50	603	16077
	1.43	0.67	804	37900
	2.14	0.88	1275	67657
	2.86	0.96	1430	75891
	3.57	1.18	1890	90032
	4.29	1.31	2163	114818

$[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

$[\text{EA}]$, $[\text{DEA}]$ and $[\text{TEA}] = 1.57, 0.98$ and 0.71 mol dm^{-3} , respectively.

the formation of the $\{\text{Fe}^{3+} \text{Amine}\}$ complex and its reaction with CCl_4 to give $\dot{\text{C}}\text{Cl}_3$ is also reported. Ruthenium(III) complexes with amines/aminoalcohols have also been confirmed during the kinetic investigations⁴.

Based on the reports the following mechanism for the initiation of Ru^{3+} catalysed polymerization of AN by AA in presence of CCl_4 is proposed.

Table 3. Activation parameters for the Ru^{III} catalysed polymerization of AN with AA in presence of $[\text{CCl}_4]$

Aminoalcohol	E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	$\log A$	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol^{-1})	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})
Ethanolamine	57.0 ± 0.5	9.30	55.0 ± 0.5	-67.0 ± 1.0	76.05 ± 0.5
Diethanolamine	48.0 ± 0.5	8.00	45.0 ± 0.5	-93.0 ± 1.0	76.0 ± 0.5
Triethanolamine	42.0 ± 0.5	7.10	39.0 ± 0.5	-108.0 ± 1.0	75.5 ± 0.5

$[\text{AN}] = 2.86 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RuCl}_3] = 2.86 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CCl}_4] = 0.97 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

$[\text{EA}]$, $[\text{DEA}]$ and $[\text{TEA}] = 1.57, 0.98$ and 0.71 mol dm^{-3} , respectively.

Scheme 1

$R_1R_2R_3N^+Cl^-$ formed in steps (3) and (5) may undergo dissociation in the polar solvent DMSO to give $R_1R_2R_3N^+$, which reacts with CCl_4 to produce $\dot{C}Cl_3$ as suggested by Takemoto and coworkers⁵.

The charge-transfer complex could not be detected in the polymerization systems, because they are too reactive, and therefore we have explored the possibility of formation of both the charge-transfer complexes viz. complex between $\{Ru^{3+}-AA\}$ and CCl_4 and complex between $\{Ru^{3+}-AA\}$ and monomer.

According to the Scheme 1

$$(C_{\text{complex}}) = K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] \quad (8)$$

On applying the steady state conditions to (I_1) and (I_2) we get,

$$[I_1] = \frac{k_1 K_2 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [CCl_4]}{\{k_{-2} + k_3[M]\}} \quad (9)$$

and

$$[I_2] = \frac{k_4 K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [M]}{\{k_{-4} + k_5[CCl_4]\}} \quad (10)$$

If α is the fraction of the (C_{complex}) used for the formation of (I_1) , $(1-\alpha)$ becomes the fraction used for the formation of (I_2) , then the rate of formation of (\dot{R}) may be given as,

$$\frac{d[\dot{R}]}{dt} = \alpha k_3 [I_1] [M] + (1-\alpha) k_5 [I_2] [CCl_4] \quad (11)$$

On substituting the value of $[I_1]$ and $[I_2]$ from eqs. (9) and (10) in eq. (11) we get,

$$\frac{d[\dot{R}]}{dt} = \frac{\alpha k_2 k_3 K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [CCl_4] [M]}{\{k_{-2} + k_3[M]\}^{1/2}} + \frac{(1-\alpha) k_4 k_5 K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [M] [CCl_4]}{\{k_{-4} + k_5[CCl_4]\}} \quad (12)$$

Assuming bimolecular termination, the rate of initiation may be given as :

$$R_i = \frac{1}{k_t^{1/2}} \left[\frac{\alpha k_2 k_3 K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [CCl_4] [M]}{\{k_{-2} + k_3[M]\}^{1/2}} + \frac{(1-\alpha) k_4 k_5 K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [M] [CCl_4]}{\{k_{-4} + k_5[CCl_4]\}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

The overall rate of polymerization (R_p) can be expressed as,

$$R_p = k_p [M] R_i \quad (14)$$

or

$$R_p = \frac{k_p}{k_t^{1/2}} [M] \left[\frac{\alpha k_2 k_3 K_1 [Ru^{3+}] [AA] [CCl_4] [M]}{\{k_{-2} + k_3[M]\}} + \frac{(1-\alpha) k_4 k_5 [Ru^{3+}] [AA]^{1/2} [M] [CCl_4]}{\{k_{-4} + k_5[CCl_4]\}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (15)$$

where, k_p and k_t represent the rate of propagation and termination, respectively.

When charge-transfer complex (I_1) predominates, α may be taken as unity and eq. (15) reduces to;

$$R_p = \frac{k_p}{k_t^{1/2}} (k_2 k_3 K_1)^{1/2} \frac{[Ru^{3+}]^{1/2} [AA]^{1/2} [CCl_4]^{1/2} [M]^3}{\{k_{-2} + k_3[M]\}^{1/2}} \quad (16)$$

Since step (3) is fast therefore, inequality $k_3[M] \gg k_{-2}$ holds and eq. (16) becomes eq. (17).

$$R_p = \frac{k_p}{k_t^{1/2}} (k_2 K_1)^{1/2} [Ru^{3+}]^{1/2} [AA]^{1/2} [CCl_4]^{1/2} [M] \quad (17)$$

Eq. (17) is in application under the condition $[CCl_4]/[AA] \leq 1$.

On the other hand, when the charge-transfer complex (I_2) predominates, α may be taken as zero, and eq. (15) reduce to

$$R_p = \frac{k_p}{k_t^{1/2}} (k_4 k_5 K_1)^{1/2} \frac{[Ru^{3+}]^{1/2} [AA]^{1/2} [M]^{3/2} [CCl_4]^{1/2}}{\{k_{-4} + k_5 [CCl_4]\}^{1/2}} \quad (18)$$

Since step (5) is fast, the inequality $k_5[CCl_4] \gg k_{-4}$, holds and eq. (18) reduces to

$$R_p = \frac{k_p}{k_t^{1/2}} (k_4 k_5)^{1/2} [Ru^{3+}]^{1/2} [AA]^{1/2} [M]^{3/2} \quad (19)$$

which is applicable under the conditions $[CCl_4]/[AA] > 1$.

Experimental

Purification of AN (SDs) and CCl_4 (E. Merck) was done by standard method. DMSO (E. Merck) extra pure grade was used without further purification. EA, DEA and TEA of A.R. grade (E. Merck) were used as such. Stock solution of $RuCl_3$ (Loba, A.R. grade) was prepared by dissolving the sample in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} HCl and was stored in black bottles to avoid photochemical effects.

The polymerization of AN was carried out in a dilatometer (bulb capacity 5 ml, with a 11 cm long capillary of 3 mm diameter) under nitrogen atmosphere using DMSO as solvent. The required amounts of AN, AA, $RuCl_3$ and DMSO were taken in the dilatometer and placed in thermostatic water bath maintained at desired temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$). The progress of the reaction was monitored with the help of a cathetometer by recording meniscus movement (i.e. unit volume per unit time). The product of the reaction was precipitated with methanol and dried to constant weight.

The rate of polymerization (R_p) of AN is given^{1,6} as,

$$R_p \text{ (mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}) = \frac{w \times 10^3}{t \times 60 \times 53.06} \quad (i)$$

where, w is weight of polymer obtained from 1 ml of AN (molecular weight 53.06 and specific gravity 0.805). If C is the percentage conversion and t is the time (in minutes) of polymerization, then

$$C = \frac{w \times 100}{t \times 0.805} \quad (ii)$$

The value of w obtained from eq. (ii), on substitution in eq. (i) yields,

$$R_p = \frac{0.805 \times C \times 10^3}{100 \times t \times 60 \times 53.06} \quad (iii)$$

or

$$R_p = \frac{2.52 \times 10^{-3} \times C}{t} \quad (iv)$$

In actual experiments, C was obtained from a master graph plotted between volume contraction and percentage conversion. The percentage conversion thus obtained was plotted against time to calculate R_p .

The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]_{\text{int}}$ of polymer was determined in dimethylformamide solution at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ using and Ubbelohde viscometer.

The viscosity average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) was calculated by using the Mark-Houwink equation :

$$[\eta]_{\text{int}} = KM^\alpha$$

where the values⁷ of K and α are 20.9×10^5 and 0.75, respectively. Further, the average degree of polymerization (\bar{P}_n) was calculated from \bar{M}_v .

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